

National Strength On Construction Of International Freight Terminal In Entikong Indonesia

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze social strength elements in supporting the construction of an international freight terminal in Entikong, Indonesia. Data collection obtained from interviews and literature studies that are relevant to the discussion in this paper. The results of the study are analyzed into two elements of national strength based on Jablonsky's theory (2008: 148); (1) the determinants of natural forces include (a) geography that creates opportunities based on proximity to the Malaysian state, (b) natural resources in the border area of Entikong can support potential new development in the industrial sector that supports the construction of international freight terminals; and (2) Determinants of Social Strength among others the economy by opening access to economic sector development along the border area of Entikong and Tebedu Malaysia.

Index Terms: National strength, international freight terminal, Entikong.

1 INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country in the world and has direct borders with ten countries, both bordering the land and sea area. The area included as a border area spread to 12 provinces in Indonesia. There are 38 regencies and cities located in the land border area that borders other countries geographically and demographically. The existence of these border areas requires special attention from interested parties at the local or central level. Most of the country's land borders with Malaysia are found on the island of Borneo. Indonesia's land border area in Kalimantan, one of which is Entikong, has potential. The construction of the Indonesian Entikong border area is a welfare symbol of people in the region. Meanwhile, the border communities in Indonesia themselves, especially the border areas that are directly confronted with Malaysia, have a different level of welfare gap, Malaysia's development is more advanced than the Indonesian border. This is evidenced by the many Entikong border communities who are looking for jobs to Malaysia or shopping in Malaysia because the border area is more modern there. National strength is defined as a concept of geopolitics that reflects the picture and potential amount that exists [1]. The area of the national boundary is a strategic area in defense and security for a country, including an area that is very vulnerable to transnational crime. Then, other potentials that are also owned by the border area are potential economic value resources such as forestry, mining, marine, and tourism. This potential can be indicated to be a national power of a country. National strength is the concept of geopolitics, reflects the mass characteristics of a nation which is the sum of their abilities and potential [1].

Regions that have national power, both in the land border area and the sea border area. Besides, the existence of human resources that also need to be managed so that border management is fulfilled comprehensively and responsibly. The construction urgency of the border area in Entikong should be a warning to the regional and central government. The many potentials that are not maximally utilized at the Entikong border are not only economic potential, but also geographic development potential and natural and local resource potential. The perspective of local economic development in the context of developing border areas is needed for the study and formulation of Entikong international freight final policies which are considered sufficient for function realization border region itself, one of which is to create prosperity for local communities by relying on maximum economic growth in the border region. With the potential of the international goods terminal, Entikong allegedly will trigger the development of locally-based economic development in the Entikong area. This will have an impact on the growing development of the Entikong border area. Also, Malaysia has owned the Inland Port, which was built to facilitate international trade by promoting access to international transportation and supporting national economic development plans at the border. The existence of Inland port Malaysia is more focused on international trade, while Indonesia cross-border is more generally containing various aspects so that its operations have obstacles for both to interact. Therefore, the researcher indicated that the potential of Entikong border area in the construction of international freight terminal as a supporter of the national power of the Indonesian border region in the aspect of natural power and social strength in development requires comprehensive assessment through elements within the national power itself. Based on this, the research aims to analyze the social power element in supporting the construction of the Entikong Indonesia international freight terminal.

2 METHODOLOGY

The method approach in this research is a descriptive qualitative approach. This research study focuses on International Freight Terminal construction in Entikong border area, Indonesia. Field data collection techniques utilizing interviews, and literature studies. This research data comes from primary data obtained by conducting research in the field

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and secondary data collected through references in the book literature and scientific journals. This article further highlights the current situation of the International Freight Terminal construction in Entikong Border.

3 DISCUSSION

3.1. National Strength Elements in Supporting International Freight Terminal Construction

There are two sub-principal elements of national strength, namely (1) the aspect of natural strength determination contains a discussion in geography and natural resources form, and (2) the element of determination of social strength in economics form [2]. Both of these determinant elements have their respective points related to changes in the environment that are influenced by individual behavior. Further regarding this opinion, explained as follows.

3.1.1. Natural Strength Determinants

Geography

The cross-border post of Entikong State has become a strategic area with the presence of formal border access. This affects the movement and migration of freight, services and human commodities. Increased migration of cargo, services and people occurs in both inflows and outflows through the official border gate and through the traditional border gate. Then, outflows and inflows of goods and services indicate an increase in years which is dominated by goods entry into Indonesia. Whereas the products flow more inflow than out. Therefore, the central government cooperates with the regional government to initiate the construction of an International Freight Terminal which will handle import exports in Entikong border area. National strength defined in more detail is state ability, potential, and capacity in utilizing material and spiritual wealth in achieving national interests [1]. The construction of international freight terminals is closely related to the geography of Indonesia which is directly dealing with Malaysia, for that Indonesia has the ability, potential and capacity to take advantage of these opportunities. Geographical factors in natural power determinants are location, climate or size and topography that affect the views of a country's capacity. The intended site is foreign policy related to the relationship between foreign policy and location. This is very fundamental so that it raises geopolitics as a science. The area is also closely related to the climate, which in turn has a significant influence on national power. The most impoverished countries in the modern era are almost all located outside the temperate climate zone either in the tropics or the cold area. Indonesia's geographical - strategic conditions on the international trade route are allegedly creating separate opportunities for the advancement of Indonesia's border region. Some land border areas become opportunities that can be used to improve the welfare of the community. Therefore, the lack of supporting infrastructure facilities in Entikong can cause constraints to development. Entikong's land border area which is geographically bordered directly is limited only by the boundaries of the sovereignty symbol of each country providing a geographical-strategic threat. The more complete facilities and infrastructure at the border, the easier access to international markets, the geographical opportunity referred to is the development of human resources and infrastructure at the border to become

management targets in developing the border area. Improved human resources are relied on to contribute to the efforts to develop International Goods Terminals. The community in the form of size, trends and structure is an essential aspect of the national power element in the construction of this international freight terminal. Large populations are a crucial prerequisite, but not an automatic guarantee of strength. In the future, global trends will also affect the structure and balance of the national population, especially in the poorest countries. Even so, the structure and stability of the society are also important for developed countries. Significant here is the percentage of the population in the most productive group, generally considered to be between the ages of 18 and 45 years, which can meet the needs of the nation's military and industry as well as possible and create the next generation. Problems of public interest. This is naturally the case in the border region because each country has its claims related to areas that have been marked with boundary stakes which sometimes move and are considered detrimental to Indonesia or Malaysia. Some of the First International Goods Terminal functions, as the entrance door to the Indonesia-Malaysia border area and goods as a way out or into the port of products. The gate is an official route legalized concerning Indonesian law to become a vehicle for trade traffic. The process of entry and exit of goods has several customs and quarantine stages arranged at the port. In addition to passing the procedure, the entry and exit of products is called illegal or unofficial. Second, as a flow cycle for the transfer of goods or cargo that is channeled effectively and efficiently by land transportation and sea transportation as a facility to transport goods out and in the customs area. The link has three elements, including (1) transferring cargo to the hauling truck from the cargo ship, (2) the transfer of goods is more time-efficient and (3) the costs are more economical. This function is intended to deliver the products twice at the port. The transportation process uses both mechanical and non-mechanical devices as auxiliary tools for moving goods from trucks to ships or trucks to trains or vice versa. So, the process of shipping the products is done twice to be dismantled and re-loaded which is called face to face. Third, as an opening to the industrial potential of a well-organised and well-developed port industry that develops the possibility of other businesses, this will cause the port area not only to be an area for exchanging goods and services but also a new dry port industrial zone. Its function has a positive impact and many benefits for most countries in the world, some positive impacts. The Indonesian government, especially at the border of Entikong, can develop the International Goods Terminal located on its borders to increase competition in the trade sector in the country while at the same time increasing the regional and state economy. The benefits gained from the use of the International Goods Terminal include increasing the capacity and level of port production, congestion around the port decreases, areas prone to traffic accidents are reduced, saving road maintenance costs, reducing the risk of environmental damage, can contain seven more practical containers and saving transaction costs for shippers. International Goods Terminal Development can be carried out on industrial area access to the International Goods Terminal or vice versa, where shipping of goods from the sea to the mainland can be done more efficiently.

Natural resources

Strength is the capacity of the state to take control of the attitude of other countries [3]. Natural resources dominate national power although it is also a national goal that is used by the government to strengthen and develop its national interests [1]. Indonesia's border areas are indicated to have abundant natural resources, including the outer regions which directly deal with other countries in this study, namely the border area in Entikong. In the Act states that Natural Resources owned by sea and land areas in this border region should be optimized for their utilization to improve the regional and central economy, and enhance the welfare of local communities. Entikong border area has the potential to strategically develop the economic sector in the field of export and import. This is supported by formal access so that it can grow rapidly and rapidly. Border areas based on the wealth of local natural resources can be developed for economic growth by developing sectors that not only provide benefits for one but benefit both countries, namely Indonesia and Malaysia [4]. The border area of Entikong favored the availability of natural resources with minimal management, besides that Malaysia first welcomed globalization by building its borders more modernly. The existence of Inland Port, one of which was the answer from Malaysia to face the interaction behavior of the Entikong border community with Malaysia which has a connection to each other. The development of the Lintas Batas Post area began with the inauguration of the Entikong border area on February 25, 1991. The construction of the area was marked by the existence of a road connection from Entikong to the Tebedu area. Then there is a difference between the State Border Crossing narrative and the narrative of the Border Examination Door. In this case, it can be explained that the National Transboundary Post is the door for accessing the entrance and entry point for the Indonesian and Malaysian countries \ done traditionally. The required documents are like a passport or commonly referred to as a local person as a Cross-border Pass. Meanwhile, the Cross-border Checkpoint Besides, the Cross-border Checkpoint itself also has the function of accessing and leaving between countries using official permission. Through large amounts of natural resources, it is essential for a modern country to fight, to operate an industrial base, and to respect other international actors through trade and assistance, whether in current industrial products or in the raw material itself. But these resources, whether they are fertile land and water or coal and oil, are not evenly distributed throughout the world and are increasingly scarce. Besides, as in the case of geopolitical ownership from strategic places, the physical property of natural resources is not always a source of strength unless a nation can also develop these resources and maintain political control over their dispositions. The combination of rapid industrial growth and a decline in resources has transformed the global economy into a seller's market while providing a sizeable economic influence for countries that control essential commodities. The community utilizes the wealth of natural resources in the border area by managing creative industrial models that can increase competitiveness in the international market, Establishment of International Goods Terminal facilitates access to accommodation and transportation of goods without having to transit and can streamline the cost of distribution of products. Use of natural resources wisely, Wealth of resources natural resources are an opportunity for the development of the International Goods Terminal which

facilitates access to international trade, the easier access to exchange goods and services will further increase the intensity of export and import. Natural resources can be utilized with planned processing for the long term. The state should be able to determine the legitimacy of the ability of the protection system for its people, both vertically and horizontally. In essence the country is a coherent entity in one unit even though it has several components such as territorial, government and citizens [5]. Constraints that occur later in the framework of the development of natural resource-based border areas are constrained by policies and infrastructure readiness that have not supported. Strategies developed in the structure of the development of border areas include supporting the establishment of regulations and conducive operations in the field of natural resources in the border area of Entikong. Besides, encouraging the central and regional governments to compile a working map for effective spatial planning and to spur proper operations based on the region and the roadmap of natural resource potential areas. Another thing that was developed was implementing responsive development reforms on infrastructure for what is needed by an area (hard & soft), mapping and enhancing the roles of various leading sectors (both products and services) and motivating growth for other industries and prioritizing focus on sustainability development Human Resources, as well as being a facilitator of internal and external trade development. One of the main things in the development of Alaman resources based on the Entikong border is by building internal and external trade facilities, in this case, is the construction of an international-based Port or Goods Terminal. The urgency of the structure of international freight terminals sees that the potential of the Entikong border is to become an integrated import and export place, where there is a dimension of increasing the resources of the two countries (Indonesia and Malaysia). Negotiations between the two countries to jointly discuss the follow-up to the construction of the International Goods Terminal in the border area of Entikong, this is due to the change of government in Malaysia. Then, the absence of standard operating procedures (SOP) from the ministry to date has also become part of the problem in the construction of the International Goods Terminal at the Entikong border. Later, the readiness of the International Goods Terminal operation at the Entikong Border is still prepared in the form of a Ministerial Regulation (Permen) from the ministry trade, which will become an actor in export and import through international freight terminals at the Entikong border. Then regarding the minimum transaction of 600 RM in the Indonesia Border Trade Agreement cooperation agreement with Malaysia, it is currently in the revision stage, so that with the International Goods Terminal it could be abolished. Based on the explanation from the Director General of Land Transportation, Sub Directorate of Goods Terminal Transportation, the Ministry of Transportation said that in July 2018 the physical construction of the International Goods Terminal was 60%, and is expected to be completed by the end of this year. To develop local natural resources in the Entikong border area, there are several important aspects to consider regarding the Malaysian market, the potential elements of local commodities or an area, the strength of national domestic investment, security of internal security (domestic) or external (overseas). So that the existence of the International Goods Terminal will be the center of growing natural resources in the border area, and the Entikong border will be a role model for the

development of border areas in other land border areas. With the existence of the International Goods Terminal, it also strengthens relations with neighboring countries, as a country that lives side by side and is still a family, Indonesia and Malaysia conduct diplomacy through cooperative relations in the economic field. Indonesia cannot be a closed country of international relations, especially with the Malaysian State which is in the same geographic structure and is only distinguished by the sovereignty lines. Infrastructure availability and support from the International Goods Terminal facilitate the pattern of economic interaction between the two countries which are competitive.

3.2. Determinants of Social Strength in Economics Forms

Economic capacity and development are the main links to the determinants of natural and social power. Regarding natural resources, as we have seen, a nation can be blessed well but cannot turn these resources into military hardware, high-tech exports, and other manifestations of power. Ultimately, however, economic development in a nation flows from the social determinants of power, whether it is the comprehensive modernization of politics and formal education, or geographical and social mobility and acceptance of ready-made innovations. To increase exports that can provoke economic development in the border area of Entikong, the opportunity to develop International Goods Terminals is seen from a financial standpoint based on the strategic role of the International Goods Terminal indicated to be able to increase international trade activities, especially for local businesses. same with various different sectors, in terms of facilitating international trade these two countries also have the facilities available, Malaysia with inland ports and the Government of Indonesia to build International Goods Terminals increasingly promote international trade activities between Indonesia and Malaysia so as to provide opportunities for border communities to open independent industries to develop its economy in order to improve the welfare of the community. After the border area becomes the center of business, automatically the income of the border region people also increases along with the full access to international markets. Although economic activity in the Entikong border area was relatively high, it turned out that the local market was getting weaker because of the low domestic supply which resulted in low-income levels of the Indonesian people in Entikong. Goods from abroad enter without the provision of maximum limits beating local products that have not been maximally developed due to lack of public knowledge. International Goods Terminal Opportunities will provide communities concerning increasing domestic productivity by utilizing available resources so that the Entikong border community can boost exports and household welfare. Entikong Border Area is a pilot area or role model in the development of a border area with the construction of an International Goods Terminal. This condition can also be seen from the typology border of the Entikong region which has the characteristic that there is economic connectivity between the boundaries of two countries, then the condition of a bottleneck infrastructure, as well as not integrated policy framework. This means that there is no comprehensive monitoring in mapping the potentials of export goods which will be a prima donna resource in the Entikong region. This was acknowledged by representatives of the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture who stated that there

was no comprehensive mapping to target border products that have an export potential for Malaysia. Border areas require accelerating economic growth to create a prosperous border region through the construction of international freight terminals. The Entikong-Sarawak border area is directly linked although the growth and development of the Sarawak region are more advanced and has universal appeal for the border communities of Entikong, especially West Kalimantan. Based on this linkage, it became a reference for Entikong, causing changes in the economic sector of the Entikong border towards a better direction. Some important things and become a crucial point of development in the border region is that there is attention that focuses on the network, the flow of mobility, and the flow of globalization which is then described as the characteristics of the border region. This key component is significant in understanding the context of development in the border region as a whole [6]. The construction of the International Goods Terminal is one of the agendas in resolving the problems of trade relations between Indonesia and Malaysia. The government implements the concept of responsibility to protect the idea of humanity and the capacity to act effectively to protect its citizens from economic threats [7]. Thus the government plays a role in bridging the financial activities of its people, the interrelationships and a sense of mutual need between Indonesian border communities and Malaysia's border to meet their individual needs keeps the trade flow in both countries going on. This condition requires special attention by the role of the state in developing the Entikong border area seriously. Entikong which is the Center for National Strategic Activities and has strategic potential in economic development at the local and global level, and at the same time serves as a protection for border areas. Efforts to increase economic growth in the border region collide with the side of environmental conservation where infrastructure development then degrades the ecological protection function. The principle of sustainable development, in this case, is to implement the sustainability of the social, economic and environmental aspects. According to information obtained from the Director General of Land Transportation of the Terminal Freight Transportation Sub-Directorate, Ministry of Transportation, the State faced obstacles, and the main priority was land acquisition by the Ministry of Public Works and People's Housing, then the absence of normalization of trade in the Entikong border area (discourse on whether the International Goods Terminal is only intended for the exchange of goods between Indonesia and Malaysia alone, or will be the center of export and import to various international countries). Then, things that need to be considered are the possibilities for the occurrence of market distortion and osmosis phenomena in the economic flow of the region at the Entikong border. Some rules and policies limit trade in Entikong, this makes the market reach not optimal. In the context of the system, this is still under investigation by the trade ministry with trade restrictions with the Malaysian trade ministry. Then, the osmosis of phenomena that occurred in Entikong resulted in limited infrastructure which eventually led in products and services sent from Indonesia to Malaysia through non-formal (illegal) roads. The impact is on the economic disparity between the Entikong border, Indonesia and Sarawak, Malaysia. This happens because Sarawak has added value from the marketed products. The phenomenon of distortion and osmosis that occurs is an indication of the importance of improving and providing adequate infrastructure and

regulations, thus minimizing disparities in the Entikong border area going forward. The existence of the International Goods Terminal construction project is one of the improvements for infrastructure provision in the border area to minimize disparity conditions. Then, effective regulations related to the construction of the International Goods Terminal are still being worked on by relevant ministries and institutions. Overall, the export-import discourse at the Entikong border international Goods Terminal will become a foreign trade policy that will later collaborate with various departments and institutions, including the Ministry of Agriculture's role, in which the agricultural products at the Entikong border become a prima donna. But so far it has not been optimized, for example regarding product processing, packaging, and others. The International Goods Terminal has the same functions as a seaport, which is a terminal for the exchange of goods and services and has customs services so that cargo transfers become more efficient. All activities related to the cargo at the International Goods Terminal are then proceeded through containers that function to collect goods packaging goods, handling goods to the ship, security of products and guarantee the integrity of the products to the seaport using vehicles or land transportation that transports all goods for the cargo was transferred to the ship at the port. The Government of Indonesia built the International Goods Terminal in the border area of Entikong to expedite international economic activities in the region, the development of border areas is no longer limited to the Post of State Boundaries but the government develops it in the form of a dry port of International Goods Terminal which generally has a liaison function between countries and at the same time complete customs services, trading activities that occur in the border area of Entikong experience dynamic development. Based on the potential and area of the construction of the International Goods Terminal namely Entikong Subdistrict, an area that is directly adjacent to the Malaysian State, the pattern of the relationship is bilateral because it involves the two countries. In the perspective of international relations, the construction of the International Goods Terminal is a foreign political, economic policy because it discusses the correlation between the State and the market. In the construction of the International Goods Terminal, researchers indicated that there was an international trade gap occurring in Entikong, that is, the Entikong community is still an active consumer of Malaysian products while the export level is low and weakens the resilience of the border economy. The Indonesian government takes action to regulate the economic gap involving the existing political autonomy in one system or the same way, or with the International Goods Terminal, the Indonesian government intends to expand the market and also wants to increase economic growth with the mechanism of export-import prices through the construction of International Goods Terminals. In analyzing the construction of the International Goods Terminal at the Entikong border, researchers found various perspectives from the perspective of an international political economy. Each region has a market that becomes a community shopping center, the entry and exit of goods for sale. This market is one of the reasons for populist economic growth in Entikong District. The community knows the Entikong Tent Market, where all the activities of exchanging and selling from neighboring countries in this market. This market is expected to be a driving force for development in the border region by developing agricultural, plantation,

agricultural and handicraft products from the people for sale through the International Goods Terminal. Simply put, the border area is defined as a legal-political unit that functions unique and strategically for a country [8]. In the context of this kind of understanding, Blanchard also sees other functions of the border, such as military and strategic, economic, constitutive, identity, and national unity and development in the state and local interests. The border function in the economic field is then used as a state control function related to capital flows, trade activities of several countries, the presence of foreign investment, and the flow of movement of types of goods and services between countries. The border economic function is also a legal way for border areas to utilize natural resources. Holsti's view supports this as the first to view a science beyond the traditional point of view of assessing the state as the only role in the international system [9]. This means that the policy of a country is very influential on the existing international system both to achieve national and regional and global interests. In the framework of the development of land border areas in the territory of Indonesia, a model has been developed that is applied to the border region so that it is useful and developed according to the elements of national power at the border. These potentials are central to the growth of the community and global economic sector, transit, research centers and nature tourism and border tourism, and agropolitan development. Then, in the model mentioned, several components form the border area, including Lintas Bata Post, land port (International Goods Terminal), nature tourism and cultural tourism, agriculture, bounded zone or bonded zone, industrial area, and welcome plaza. Construction of the International Goods Terminal in Entikong, currently BNPP is carrying out coordination between ministries and institutions of interest that directly or indirectly contribute to this development. The construction of international freight terminals is aimed at increasing opportunities for economic growth through export and import of goods and services abroad.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The element of national power in the development of the border region, especially welcoming the construction of the Entikong International Goods Terminal, is alleged to be a turning point in the development of the Entikong border area based on port land, where the main economic activities of concern are community or local economy. By further enhancing the role of the leading sector, development and directed policy direction, it will naturally encourage growth in other industries. Also, efforts to maintain the existence of sustainable development and human resource development can be seen from the increasingly advanced trade facilities in Entikong, both domestic (internal) and Malaysian (external) trade. In this case, the role of the International Goods Terminal will be strategic and become the center of economic growth in the field of export and import in Entikong based on analysis through two determinants. The first Resource Determinants cover geography aspects, which means that the condition of the border area and topography and demography in it are indicated as opportunities for the construction of international freight terminals. The geographical condition of Entikong directly bordering the border area of Tebedu in Sarawak Malaysia has a relationship with each other in various aspects of the interdependent life of its people. With this closeness, building a more emotional relationship for the people of the

two border regions so that the construction of international goods terminals can be realized to build a border area. Secondly, the determinants of resources from the aspect of natural resources which means the natural resource wealth in the Entikong border area can be developed as development tools. The fact that the people of Entikong and Tebedu Malaysia have different needs cannot be denied, the Entikong people who most need production from Malaysia while Entikong provides raw materials make a related relationship and dependence on both Indonesian and Malaysian countries. Good management and development of natural resources enable the Entikong region to turn into a center for trade activities and management of state assets that have a positive impact on the region and the country. Determinants in the element of national strength which subsequently in this study are strengths social determinants which are seen from the economic aspects of integrative policies that seek to collaborate aspects of the central and regional government as well as cross-sectoral involvement for the Entikong border region as a strategic area to encourage the growth of other non-priority sectors as well do. In other words, the existence of mutually beneficial economic complementarity does not only depend on one sector. Of all the determinants in the element of national strength, the results of this study indicate that the three points analyzed both concerning geography, natural resources and economic aspects, the construction of an international goods terminal allegedly has excellent potential in the development of the Entikong border area. Through the construction of this international freight terminal, the Entikong border area can develop elements of national power that already exist and are supported by the role of the Indonesian state itself in realizing the development.

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